

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

SOCIAL DIMENSION OF RURAL AREAS

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<https://rural-interfaces.eu/maps/portugal-southwest-alentejo/>

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Summary and key messages

In this Position Paper we tried to synthesise the challenges and recommendations that were discussed by the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) Portugal Southwest (MAP SW), concerning the Social Dimension issues of the Southwest Alentejo territory.

This territory has for many years attracted many foreign citizens of various nationalities.

The extension of land near the coast, the microclimate, and the existing irrigation system, are constraints that have favoured the establishment of agricultural companies, which have found in our territory the ideal requirements to produce quality and high added value, making agriculture, particularly horticulture and small fruit production, one of the main economic activities of the municipality. Therefore, the territory attracts migrant labour because the local supply does not meet the needs of the companies based in the municipality, due to the amount of labour required and the demanding nature of the work

Particularly since the 1980s, this territory has been welcoming foreign citizens. In this decade, the area was mainly sought after by citizens from Northern Europe who settled here. The positive receptiveness of the local population, the climate and the nature were the main factors for this community to settle, seeking a quality of life that they did not have in their countries of origin.

The MAP held two meetings, both online. In the first meeting, in addition to detailed presentation of the SHERPA project, the Discussion Paper and the individual presentation of each of the MAP members, it was also possible to "focus" the discussion on the "Social Dimension" theme in two sub-themes which are regarded as the most relevant for the region: "Improving the well-being of the rural population" and "Promoting social inclusion (migrants)". The MAP members then focused the discussion on identifying the main needs related to these two sub-themes in the MAP territory.

In the second meeting, more participatory, examples of ongoing policies and initiatives conducted by actors in the region were identified, and policy recommendations and future research priorities were discussed, always related to the two identified sub-themes.

It was a very constructive discussion, mainly because it was based on very different visions about the current situation of the territory, about its future and about the priority measures that should be conducted in the future. The regional importance of the topic allows the MAP SW to be an important contribution to the construction of future European policies related to the Social Dimension of rural territories.

As regards to the well-being of rural areas, it was possible to identify the need to intervene at the level of **public responses to services to the population** and the need to make compatible the desired **economic development** with the **preservation of the natural values** of the territory.

Concerning the social inclusion of migrants, a theme on which the actors of the territory have a set of **initiatives with strong impact**, it was mainly highlighted the importance of **working in a concerted manner at national and European level**, and of seeking an **articulation with the migrants' countries of origin**, to ensure an adequate response to their expectations and to the territory.

1. Introduction

The territory covered by the MAP SW is the Odemira municipality, which is the largest municipality in Portugal and is located on the coast, in the southwest of the Alentejo region, in southern Portugal, being bordered to the west by the Atlantic Ocean, to the south by the Algarve and to the north and west by the municipalities of Sines, Santiago do Cacém (Alentejo Litoral) and Ourique (Baixo Alentejo). Administratively, the municipality belongs to the district of Beja and is integrated in the Alentejo region (NUTS II), in the sub-region of Alentejo Litoral (NUTS III).

Unlike most rural territories in Portugal, in Odemira there has been a stabilisation of the resident population, mainly due to the flow of migrant citizens who arrive in the territory, essentially through economic migration, as labour for the large agricultural companies dedicated, essentially, to the production of vegetables and red fruits, which distinguish the Odemira municipality as an exporting production pole to Europe. However, as this migration is concentrated in some areas of the territory, there is a high asymmetry within the municipality itself.

The agricultural compatibility of the companies settled in the Mira Irrigation Perimeter and, simultaneously, in the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park poses environmental, housing and social challenges. This makes the Southwest Alentejo region an excellent territory to analyse issues relating to the social dimension of rural areas and thus contribute to influence future European policies.

Mira Irrigation Perimeter (Source: DGADR)

The Mira Irrigation Perimeter covers an area of 12,000 ha of which 10,670 ha are located in the municipality of Odemira and around 1,330 ha in the municipality of Aljezur. This hydro-agricultural operation was the largest and most complex of the hydro-agricultural operations that made up the first phase of the Alentejo Irrigation Plan, presented in 1957.

The construction of the Mira Irrigation Perimeter took place between 1963 and 1973 and its management, operation and conservation are the responsibility of the Mira Beneficiaries Association.

This is a state initiative hydro-agricultural scheme classified as a Group II work, a work of regional interest of great interest for the agricultural development of the region, a classification that immediately reflects its importance for the regions in which it is located, namely the Southwest Alentejo and the Vicentine Coast.

This work of agricultural hydraulics was and continues to be an important driver of economic and social development of the regions in which it is located, and involved a significant investment by the State for its construction and modernisation, with the change of the gravity irrigation system for pressure in two Irrigation Blocks, improving the efficiency of water use and therefore soil and water conservation.

The Southwest Alentejo territory has soil and climate conditions that, together with the existence of quality irrigation water from the Mira Irrigation Perimeter, provides exceptional conditions for horticulture, fruit and flower growing, outdoors or protected, without the need, in the latter case, for systems of great environmental conditioning, normally using light structures of low environmental conditioning for the type of culture practiced, such as high tunnels, tunnels and greenhouses or shelters and much less frequently the use of greenhouses.

The Mira Irrigation Perimeter is partly within the area of the Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park

Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park (Source: ICNF)

This Protected Area, with a great diversity of coastal habitats, was classified in 1988 (having assumed the classification of Natural Park in 1995) to preserve its diversity, which translates into the presence of a flora enriched by the presence of various endemic species and a fauna in which the birdlife and ichthyofauna play an important role.

The Southwest Alentejo and Vicentine Coast Natural Park occupies an area of 89,568.77 ha (60,577.25ha of land area and 28,991.52ha of marine area) extending along a narrow strip of coastline - Southwest Coast - between S. Torpes and Burgau. The Southwest Coast, as this zone is sometimes called, corresponds to a sea-land interface zone with very specific characteristics that give it a high landscape diversity, including some habitats that support a high biodiversity, both floristic and faunistic.

The hydrographic network of the Southwest Coast is made up of watercourses belonging to the hydrographic basin of the Mira River and the hydrographic basin of the Barlavento Algarvio, which is made up of some temporary atypical systems that support a high number of species of flora and fauna, including some priority and endemic fish species. Its riparian galleries constitute a relevant habitat for the migration of transharaian passerines as well as for the feeding and refuge of various species of mammals. But, not more important, are some estuaries with their nursery areas for several fish species, as a privileged feeding, resting and nesting habitat for migratory birds.

Regarding economic aspects, the primary sector stands out, linked to agricultural and livestock activities. Much of the area is occupied by agricultural land, mostly traditional systems, and crops, with the exception of the area occupied by the Mira Irrigation Perimeter, where the availability of water has allowed the conversion and intensification of production systems.

2. Current situation based on background research and evidence

Portugal is predominantly a rural country, with urban areas concentrated mainly along the coast. Portugal concentrates about 60% of its population within 25 km of the coast. Only Lisbon has a population of over 500,000 inhabitants, and the metropolitan areas of Lisbon (with 2.8 million people) and Oporto (with 1.8 million) concentrate about 45% of the total population living on the continent. In fact, of the 85 municipalities located less than 25 km from the coast, only 19 of them have a population of more than 100,000 inhabitants.

In the entire interior of Portugal, only the district capitals and some small medium-sized towns do not fit into rural regions. Of the 122 inland Portuguese cities, only 10 have more than 100 thousand inhabitants, and about 85% have less than 50 thousand, which places them in the category of small / medium-sized cities. This leads to a very marked urbanisation process and the inability to rejuvenate rural areas.

If we look at the population density, which in Portugal is slightly higher than the European average, we can see that the population has decreased in rural areas during the last decade. But what is more relevant is that some of the rural areas (at

Figure 1 - Rural and Urban Areas in Portugal

NUTS3 level) have population densities below 30 people per square kilometre, especially in the south and north of Portugal.

Figure 2 - Evolution of population density in the EU, in Portugal and in Portuguese Rural areas (left) and Population Density of some NUTS3 in Portugal (right) (Source: Eurostat, 2018)

The Portuguese rural areas have their economy very much centred on the primary sector. If we compare this with a level of employment in the primary sector of 4.4% at European level, we realise that in Portugal this indicator is more than double. Moreover, if we look at rural areas, and despite a contraction in recent years, we have values around four times higher. And there is a wide range of regions where employment in the primary sector exceeds 20% and represents almost half of all employment in some regions.

Figure 3 - Evolution of the % of employment in the primary sector in Portugal and in Portuguese Rural areas (left) and the % of employment in the primary sector in some NUTS3 in Portugal (right) (Source: Eurostat, 2017)

Regarding the Municipality of Odemira, where the MAP SW is focused, we see that the resident population has remained relatively stable, mainly due to the doubling of the employability of the companies in the municipality, which allowed for a growth in turnover from 400 Million Euros in 2014 to almost 700 Million Euros in 2020, with more than 200 Million Euros of exports.

		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
População residente (nº) Resident population (no.)	2014 = 100	25 431	25 135	24 917	24 741	24 621	24 717
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	98,8	98,0	97,3	96,8	97,2
			-1,2	-0,9	-0,7	-0,5	0,4
Densidade populacional (habitantes / km2) Population density (Inh / km2)	2014 = 100	14,8	14,6	14,5	14,4	14,3	14,4
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	98,8	98,0	97,3	96,8	97,2
			-1,2	-0,9	-0,7	-0,5	0,4
População ≥ 65 anos (%) Population ≥ 65 years (%)	2014 = 100	26,9	27,1	27,2	27,5	27,6	27,4
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	100,6	101,0	102,3	102,4	101,7
			0,6	0,4	1,3	0,1	-0,7
Pessoal ao serviço nas empresas (nº) Persons employed in enterprises (no.)	2014 = 100	8 289	9 571	9 475	10 556	12 238	15 077
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	115,5	114,3	127,3	147,6	181,9
			15,5	-1,0	11,4	15,9	23,2
Volume de negócios nas empresas (10 ³ Euros) Turnover of enterprises (10 ³ Euros)	2014 = 100	397 150,3	430 479,1	472 987,0	539 478,8	610 298,3	684 789,4
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	108,4	119,1	135,8	153,7	172,4
			8,4	9,9	14,1	13,1	12,2
Ganho médio mensal por trabalhador por conta de outrem (Euros) Average monthly earning per employee (Euros)	2014 = 100	850,6	825,9	836,9	875,7	924,1	...
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	97,1	98,4	103,0	108,6	...
			-2,9	1,3	4,6	5,5	...
Comércio internacional de bens - Exportações (10 ³ Euros) International trade of goods - Exports (10 ³ Euros)	2014 = 100	96 799,0	117 097,6	132 607,2	152 807,3	178 723,5	206 802,0
	t.c. (%) / g.r. (%)	100,0	121,0	137,0	157,9	184,6	213,6
			21,0	13,2	15,2	17,0	15,7

Figure 4 - Evolution of some demographic and economic indicators of the Municipality of Odemira (Source: Synthesis of Statistics | GEE | Ministry of Economy, 2020)

Agricultural activities are the largest employers in the municipality, accounting for almost 50% of jobs, along with the services sector, especially tourism-related activities. The agricultural sector is the sector that pays the best salaries in the region.

CAE Rev.3		2019
01610	Actividades dos serviços relacionados com a agricultura Agricultural service activities	1
01130	Culturas de produtos hortícolas, raízes e tubérculos Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	2
01252	Cultura de outros frutos em árvores e arbustos Growing of other trees and bush fruits	3
01192	Outras culturas temporárias, n.e. Growing of other non-perennial crops, n.e.c	4
56101	Restaurantes tipo tradicional Traditional restaurants	5
01191	Cultura de flores e de plantas ornamentais Growing of flowers and ornamental plants	6
55300	Parques de campismo e de caravanismo Camping sites, including caravan sites	7
87301	Actividades de apoio social para pessoas idosas, com alojamento Social assistance to the elderly, with accommodation	8
41200	Construção de edifícios (residenciais e não residenciais) Construction of residential and non-residential buildings	9
43210	Instalação eléctrica Electrical installation	10
47111	Comércio a retalho em supermercados e hipermercados Retail sale in supermarkets and hypermarkets	11
01290	Outras culturas permanentes Growing of other perennial crops	12
85310	Educação básica (3ª Cida) e secundária geral Basic (3 rd stage) and general secondary education	13
01112	Cultura de leguminosas secas e sementes oleaginosas Growing of leguminous crops and oil seeds	14
78200	Actividades das empresas de trabalho temporário Temporary employment agency activities	15
Nº total de TCO nas CAE consideradas Total number of employees in the inferred NACE		8 056
% no nº total de TCO do Concelho % in the Municipality's total number of employees		71,2%

Figure 5 - Some data related to employment in the Municipality of Odemira (Source: Odemira Municipal Council)

In 2014, the foreign population living in the municipality already had an important weight in relation to the total number of residents (13.0%), exceeding the national panorama (3.8%), as well as the Alentejo Litoral region (6.4%) and the other municipalities that make up this area. In the following years, 2017 and 2019, the panorama is maintained, being Odemira the municipality with the highest percentage of foreign population with resident status, in 2017, 19.8% and, in 2019, 33.1%, a value well above the values presented in the remaining territories, either at national or regional level.

In 2014, the Bulgarian nationality was the most expressive in the municipality, followed by Thai and German. The nationalities that had the largest increase in their population in the territory in the years 2014, 2017 and 2019 were Nepalese and Indian. In 2014, only 55 Nepali citizens resided in the municipality, in 2017, 480 and in 2019 1776 were registered, becoming the most representative nationality. As for Indian citizens, in

2014, only 13 citizens could be counted and in successive years they have become the second most significant nationality in the municipality.

The presence of migrant communities in the territory has forced, and will force, people, businesses and public services to adapt to a new reality, with distinct challenges and needs, requiring different dynamics and strategies, seeking that local and migrant communities live together peacefully.

3. Position of the Multi-Actor Platform

At the first MAP meeting consideration was given to the four sub-themes addressed in the Discussion Paper. It was agreed, for the purpose of having an effective discussion, to focus on only two of those themes. Thus, a vote was taken, and it was decided to address the following sub-themes: 1) Improving the well-being of the rural population and 2) Promoting social inclusion (migrants).

Therefore, and whenever possible, the analysis will be presented separately for each of these sub-themes.

3.1. Identified needs

The main needs were identified for each of the sub-themes:

3.1.1. Improving the well-being of the rural population

- **Reinforcement of public services**
 - Infrastructures and public services adapted to the reality of the region - territorial dimension and resident population
 - Promote a greater sense of security - currently with a deficit of staff and means
- **Improvement of the existing transport network**
 - Need for alternative means of transport in the region (public transport)

- Need to renew the road network
- **Improve the situation of housing/accommodation in the region**
 - Increase urban perimeters
 - More accessible housing prices
- **Change the urban/rural relationship**
 - Improve the urban population's perception of the rural reality.
 - Interconnecting the population
- **Increase the knowledge about the rural population**
 - Need to investigate and monitor to scale up responses
 - Need to influence/explain the specificities of rural regions to policy makers

3.1.2. Promoting social inclusion (migrants)

- **Tackling abuses associated with mafias linked to emigration/exploitation of migrant labour**
 - Strengthening inspection and monitoring structures
 - Public policies on emigration (emphasis on family reunification)
- **Better preparation of the local community**
 - Reducing the negative impacts felt by residents
 - Work with the local community to integrate/accept migrants
- **Improve communication**
 - Lack of more objective information associated with migrant mobility
 - Communication between migrants and country of origin
- **Economic diversification**
 - Transversality (different sectors) in public investment and support in rural territories, to increase the diversity of economic activities
 - Adaptation of labour legislation to the needs of seasonal work
- **Territories and services**
 - Problems of internet network coverage/connectivity
 - Planning of the increase in territory to respond to the increase in population

3.2. Existing interventions and actions

There are already numerous public interventions related to the Social Dimension in the MAP territory, among which we can highlight the following:

- Municipal Plan for the Integration of Migrants (<https://www.cm-odemira.pt/pages/1264>)
- Strategic Plan for Cohesion and Inclusion of Migrants in Odemira (https://www.cm-odemira.pt/cmodemira/uploads/document/file/15921/manual_de_acolhimento_ao_aluno_e_encargados_de_educacao_migrantes_versao_em_ingles_.pdf)

- Intercultural Municipal Mediators Project (<https://www.acm.gov.pt/pt/-/projeto-de-mediacao-intercultural-em-servicos-publicos-misp>)
- Portuguese Language Learning (<https://www.acm.gov.pt/ru/-/como-posso-frequentar-um-curso-de-lingua-portuguesa-para-estrangeiros->) (in the territory, the most visible example is developed by Maravilha Farms in partnership with the São Teotónio Group of Schools)
- Collective [labour agreement](#) between AHSA — Association of Horticulturists, Fruticulturists and Floriculturists of the Municipalities of Odemira and Aljezur e o SETAAB - National Union of Workers in Agriculture, Forestry, Fishing, Tourism, Food Industry, Beverages and Related Fields.
- [Removable Temporary Accommodation Facilities](#) (IATA), permitted in the territory to help address the housing shortage.

In addition, local actors have developed various actions on the ground, of which we highlight the most relevant regarding the Improving the well-being of the rural population (Table 1) and to Promoting social inclusion (migrants) (Table 2).

Table 1 – Examples of actions taken by local actors | Improving the well-being of the rural population

CUI(DAR)+ | TAIPA

CUI(DAR)+ is the result of TAIPA's application to the Impact Partnership Program - Financing Instrument of the Portugal Social Innovation Mission Structure.

This initiative aims to meet the needs of carers through a support structure focused on three levels of well-being (psychological, social and physical), while also promoting awareness-raising activities, training and capacity-building workshops. This Intervention strategy focuses on the creation of a Support Office for Carers, supported by a solid and sustainable network of partnerships, whose involvement in all phases of the project is fundamental.

In this Office, the Carer can have access to psychological support and social referrals that promote their quality of life and the provision of care free of charge. The psychological counselling aims to promote strategies to deal with adversities in the provision of care, as well as to improve the psychological well-being of the Carer. Social referral will help carers to access information on existing social services and responses and their rights as informal carers and those of the people being cared for. This support can also be made available by telephone and on an itinerant basis in order to be closer to the beneficiaries.

<https://www.taipa-desenvolvimento.pt/projetos/desenvolvimento-comunitario/cui-dar/>

CLDS 4G - Geração Ativa | TAIPA

Geração Ativa is part of the Local Contracts for Social Development (CLDS 4G) program, aimed at supporting Active Ageing and Support for the Elderly Population and is aimed at those who do not receive institutional support.

The project is composed of three actions that are streamlined through different activities:

- Socio-cultural actions promoting active ageing and autonomy for the aged
- Actions to combat loneliness and isolation
- Actions to develop volunteer projects for working with populations

<https://www.taipa-desenvolvimento.pt/projetos/desenvolvimento-comunitario/clds-4g-geracao-ativa/>

Business network, trails and responsible tourism | ROTA VICENTINA

Rota Vicentina - Association for the Promotion of Nature Tourism in Alentejo and Vicentina Coast, is the entity responsible for the management, integration, stimulus, development, and promotion of the pedestrian trails of Rota Vicentina, as well as the tourist offer associated to the touristic product that Rota Vicentina represents. The association intends to affirm itself as a defining element of the region, enabling its enjoyment through one of the most natural practices to the human condition - the walk - and contributing in an unequivocal way to the sustainability of the rural world, through the dynamisation of the economic activity, stimulating the already existing activities and services, maintaining and strengthening the local traditions and culture, encouraging the creation of new businesses and promoting the destination out of the peak seasons. More recently, the offer was extended to include a system of over 1000 km of mountain bike routes, a Touring Bike route that links Lisbon and Faro airports, and various Nature, Culture and Welfare activities.

<https://rotavicentina.com/>

ID | ROTA VICENTINA

ID is a program that, through a sustainable tourism and culture network, aims to give value to what is produced and made in the territory, creating links with places, landscapes, producers, arts and craftspeople.

<https://rotavicentina.com/id/>

Table 2 – Examples of actions taken by local actors | Promoting social inclusion (migrants)

CLAIM - Local Centre for Support to the Integration of Migrants in Odemira | TAIPA

CLAIM - Local Centre for Support to the Integration of Migrants in Odemira, in its current form, is the result of a Multilateral Collaboration Protocol, signed on 10 July 2018 between a consortium of partners - TAIPA, as promoter and executing entity, and the funding entities: Odemira Municipality, "Lusomorango" Agricultural Producers Association, the agricultural companies Haygrove, Sudoberry, Vitacress and Hall Hunter, and the Temporary Work Company "Multitempo". Also included in this partnership were the parish councils of the Odemira county coast - S. Teotónio, Longueira/Almograve and Vila Nova de Milfontes. This protocol was signed based on the assumptions that a) in the field of immigrants' reception and integration, local services represent a fundamental factor, although they are and should be framed by structuring policies, in order to legitimise and guide the strategies defined at local level; b) it is mainly in the initial phase of the migratory cycle, that immigrants present specific social deficits (lack of knowledge of the language, lack of information on access to services, absence of political rights, descending professional insertion associated with difficulties in the recognition of skills...) that end up originating situations of social disadvantage and exclusion;

CLAIM is a decentralised reception, information and support office, which aims to help respond to the needs of immigrant citizens in the following areas: regularisation of migration status, nationality, family reunification, housing, work, social security, voluntary return, health, education, vocational training, entrepreneurship, support for associations,

<https://www.taipa-desenvolvimento.pt/projetos/desenvolvimento-comunitario/claim-centro-local-de-apoio-a-integracao-de-migrantes-de-odemira/>

GIRA MUNDO | TAIPA

"Gira Mundo" in this project means the movement of the world within Odemira and Odemira living, transformation and the growth of intercultural interactions. To contribute to the objective of the project, 8 actions are running, which seek to involve the maximum number of local actors and beneficiaries around a common objective. The basic methodology for most of the actions is the involvement of expressions as a means of promoting integration: gastronomy, dance, theatre, music, cinema, sport, painting, writing and video. The expressions will be a bridge for the creation of relations with the host community. Through this methodology, cultural and sporting events are promoted, commemorations, film cycles, workshops of different arts with the aim of reflecting interculturality, some informative products are created about rights and duties and moments of interaction of the migrants with the territory and the services.

"Gira Mundo" project is based on the work and reflections that have been developed in the CLAIM Odemira Consortium, which includes the Municipality of Odemira, companies (employers of migrants) and Parish Councils. These entities collaborate with the Municipal Plan for Immigrant Integration and in that sense are aware of the responsibility of local actors in the integration of migrants and the actions promoting this integration. From these companies that finance CLAIM, 4 of them are also involved in this project's co-funding proposal.

<https://www.taipa-desenvolvimento.pt/projetos/desenvolvimento-comunitario/giramundo/>

GIP – Office for the Professional Insertion of Immigrants | TAIPA

At GIP Odemira it is possible to find all kinds of support to help immigrants in their insertion or reinsertion in the labour market, namely

- Information measures on active employment and training measures, employment and training opportunities, Community programs to support mobility in employment or training
- Actions to support job search and the development of an entrepreneurial attitude
- Referrals to training actions or employment measures
- Reception and registration of offers and employment
- Introducing the unemployed to job offers
- Placement of unemployed people in job offers
- Control of the periodic submission of beneficiaries of unemployment benefits

<https://www.taipa-desenvolvimento.pt/projetos/desenvolvimento-comunitario/gip-imigrante/>

MULHERES NUMA SÓ VOZ | TAIPA

The project aims to contribute to the personal development of women, promoting the consolidation of a community that promotes intercultural values and integrates human diversity.

The project aims to be, above all, a space for expression, conviviality, integration, personal, human and even commercial development of these members of the community. To ensure their full integration, the project intends to work not only with immigrant women, but also with national women, in a space of conviviality and intercultural discovery.

<https://www.facebook.com/mulheresnumasovoz/>

PROJETO ST | TAIPA

The general objective of the ST Project is to promote social, school and community integration of migrant children and young people through the creation and promotion of collaborative responses in the parish of S. Teotónio

Its intervention is based on 3 pillars:

- Involve children and young people every year in activities that contribute to academic success and the reduction of truancy, as well as to the development of personal, social and professional skills
- To improve school results.
- Develop personal and/or social and/or cognitive skills

<https://www.taipa-desenvolvimento.pt/projetos/desenvolvimento-comunitario/projeto-st-e8g/>

LABOUR MIGRATION MANAGEMENT PROJECT | AHSA

The project "Promoting good management of labour migration to Portugal" resulted from a partnership established between AHSA and IOM - intergovernmental organisation acting in response to challenges related to human migration. This partnership aims to develop future labour migration schemes to Portugal, based on a good management of this process, to respond effectively to labour market demand, particularly in sectors (agriculture and tourism) and regions with labour shortages, seeking to promote a balance between employers' needs and the creation of safe migration paths for potential foreign workers to settle in Portugal.

Good practices in employee recruitment | Several agricultural companies

Over the years, recruitment processes have been strengthened and extended to more and more companies to ensure adequate protection for migrant workers. AHSA and Lusomorango are examples of producer organisations that have led this process.

3.3. Recommendations from the MAP

The second meeting of the MAP SW was held on the 23rd of September 2022. In this online meeting the tasks that were presented to the MAP SW members were, firstly, to identify what policy interventions are recommended to be implemented at local, regional and/or national level and how can the EU support these interventions. For the second part of this meeting, the MAP Alqueva members were asked to identify and discuss what are the knowledge gaps and what research is needed to address those.

Figure 6 - MAP SW meeting for identifying policy recommendations and knowledge and research gaps

3.3.1. Recommendations for future rural policies

One of the challenges issued to the MAP members was to identify recommended policy interventions for the SW region, to be implemented at local, regional and/or national level. The results for this exercise were as follows:

- **Local level:**
 - *Improving the well-being of the rural population*
 - Improvement of the public transport network, extending the effective use of the territory, bringing people closer to the services, fighting the concentration on the coastline.
 - Technical / HR reinforcement in local public services (SS, Finance, Health, ...) and the possibility of decentralisation to strengthen the response capacity of services in the face of population increase and the pressure it causes in access to these services.
 - Mapping and supporting diverse informal initiatives of community cooperation for the regeneration of agricultural and rural practices and support to a network of local producers with agricultural practices socially integrated in the local identity.
 - Preventing the expansion of intensive agricultural areas until negative impacts are controlled.
 - Promoting support responses for the population:
 - More vacancies in Residential Care for Older People
 - Day Centre
 - Independent living alternatives for older people
 - Creation of emergency shelter response for:
 - Victims of domestic violence
 - Homeless
 - Elderly people

- *Promoting social inclusion (migrants)*
 - Creation of delegations of monitoring, control and support entities - population and companies.
 - Local strategy co-constructed with population, able to dialogue with policy makers at central level.
 - Encouraging businesses that recruit migrants to find spaces for open and public dialogue with the local population.
 - Creating a local body to integrate entities to respond to the various sectors in the region.
 - Enhance the role of agricultural businesses in seeking answers to the various problems, as they are the ones that know the issue best and experience it on a daily basis.
- **Regional level:**
 - *Improving the well-being of the rural population*
 - Adapt public services to the resident population considering fluctuating flows.
 - Effective sectorial diversification policies.
 - Soft mobility network implemented and prepare the territory for the electric transition in transports.
 - Sectorial commitment (agriculture) to the well-being of the region's population (inter-sector articulation).
 - Auscultation of the communities with effective impacts on regional policies.
 - Reinforcement of strategies, measures, and interaction actions with the Roma community (local and other levels).
 - *Promoting social inclusion (migrants)*
 - Public housing supply integrated with changes to the Municipal Master Plan that allow private action to be (naturally) boosted.
 - Give greater sustainability to the processes of geographic dispersion of refugees.
- **National level:**
 - *Improving the well-being of the rural population*
 - Developing digital infrastructure in rural areas.
 - Agricultural policies requiring social responsibility on the part of investors.
 - Real articulation between agricultural policies and other government ministries.
 - Greater harmonisation of the interests of the different economic sectors, particularly between agriculture and tourism (the most relevant in the region), which have enormous potential for interaction and mutual promotion, investing in the diversification and identity of the territory.
 - *Promoting social inclusion (migrants)*
 - Ex-ante impact assessment of measures to be implemented.

- When defining public policies, the principles of co-development should be recovered, associating organised recruitment and destination-origin links (after evaluation studies), both at national and European level.
- Strengthen mechanisms for ethical recruitment and adapt legislation to this objective.
- Evaluation of current public policies (legislation) on migration and nationality - minimising disorganised and poorly supported migration and promote a reflection on the needs of immigrants coming to Portugal (to understand those who are not interested in staying in our country).
- Create regulations for accommodation of seasonal workers and increase the inspection of the habitability conditions of these accommodations.

3.3.2. Recommendations for future research agendas

MAP members were invited to identify knowledge gaps on the topics under discussion and which research priorities would be important to develop in the future. From this reflection, the following recommendations for future research agendas were identified:

- **Improving the well-being of the rural population**
 - Assess the socio-economic and environmental impacts of different production systems, including positive effects and negative effects, as well as the identification of possible mitigation strategies and opportunity costs associated with different options.
 - Evaluate the effects of regional agricultural development on employment generation, the type of employment generated, comparative values and retention capacity, as well as the indirect impacts associated with this phenomenon.
 - Define specific key indicators for the region, with the possibility of analysing fluctuations, that can be defined and monitored.
 - Work on the responses for the territory, which does not have a structured basis, with properly integrated targets and indicators (to avoid the risk of "perceptions").
 - Work on the concept of "Desirable Demography", at local and regional level, which can enable policy planning.
 - Try to define models for valorising endogenous resources of the territory and short commercialisation chains.
 - Measure and value the ecosystem services existing in the territory.
 - Monitor innovative community cooperation models that link rurality issues with the challenges of new generations seeking the rural environment to improve their quality of life.
 - Develop integrated studies that address the various dimensions of the well-being of rural populations (and not only with a sectoral focus).
 - Assess and define public policy measures for well-being that go beyond the local scope. The ongoing process of transferring competences in the field of social action from the Central State to the municipalities will accentuate the trend towards micro approaches and responses which, among other aspects, increase the danger of a certain fragmentation of this type of issues.
- **Promoting social inclusion (migrants)**

- Analyse/map the migrant's journey and what are the impacts of the migrant in the countries of origin.
- Research projects are needed on the phenomenon of migration should always be transnational, involving institutions from both host countries and countries of origin.
- Investigate or promote a comparative analysis of different research initiatives carried out in various territories, about the processes of international recruitment of immigrants (planned and spontaneous) for agricultural activity.
- Understand the existence, or not, of previous triple-win initiatives (destination, migrants and origin).
- Study the issues of geographical and social mobility of immigrants after arrival in the national territory.
- Evaluate the impact of the presence/absence of the migrant population on agricultural activity.
- Carry out a quantitative and qualitative survey of the local community regarding the phenomenon of immigration, with constant monitoring over time.

Conclusions

In this first cycle of MAP SW it was possible to promote a discussion between actors of the territory with very distinct visions about the concept of well-being of rural areas. However, they were unanimous in agreeing that the current social dimension within the territory is insufficient for the size of the territory and its present population.

It was possible to identify a set of needs for future policies and research initiatives that may contribute decisively to the improvement of a territory that is simultaneously prosperous from the economic point of view, while needing an improvement of the social support available to its population together with a valorisation of its existing natural capital. At this point, it is important to reinforce the potential of this territory, building upon the existence of an Irrigation Perimeter, built with strong public investment to take advantage of the recognised agricultural potential in the region, as well as a Natural Park that was set up to preserve unique natural assets that everyone wants to enhance.

Regarding the issue of social inclusion of migrants, it was also possible to identify distinct visions of the current diagnosis and existing responses. This greatly enriched the debate. It was possible to identify a vast set of initiatives, public and private, which can contribute to minimise this social inclusion problem, and which can have the ownership of all stakeholders. The responses to this kind of issue always imply that they cannot only be local or regional; it requires a response on a European scale as well as working with their countries of origin. The proposed policy measures and future research needs reinforce the need to combine a deeper knowledge of the phenomenon at local level with global complementarity, to provide adequate responses to the reality of the territory.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all the MAP Members who promptly responded to all the proposed challenges throughout this 1st cycle of the MAP SW.

This 1st cycle coincided with the period of reformulations and discussions at the level of territorial development policies and with the summer holiday period, which hampered the involvement and engagement of the different sector agents throughout the cycle. However, it is important to highlight the quality and rationale put forward by MAP members in all the proposed challenges, culminating in this Position Paper, which clearly reflects the perspectives of those on the field and those who fight daily for the territory covered by the SW MAP to achieve a better future.

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Annex 1 Methodology used by the MAP

Table 3 - Summary of the key information about the MAP

Key data	Description
Name and location of the MAP (country and region)	MAP SW (Costal SW region of Portugal)
Composition of the MAP	17 MAP Members 5 policy 5 science 7 society
Name of Facilitator	Pedro Santos
Name of Monitor	Pompeu Pais Dias
Valid period	2022-2023

Working methods and planned activities for the 1st MAP cycle

- *Creation of the MAP working group*

An invitation email was sent to the main local agents of the SW territory to create this new MAP. This email aimed to inform about the SHERPA project, its main objectives, as well as the topic to be discussed in this cycle. Each member, after accepting the invitation, sent to us the consent form, duly filled.

- *Sharing of SHERPA Discussion Paper*

The cycle's work started with share of the SHERPA Discussion Paper, translated into Portuguese and sent by email.

- *1st Meeting | online*

The agenda of this 1st meeting was:

- ✓ SHERPA: Project and Objectives
- ✓ MAP: Structure and SHERPA process
- ✓ SHERPA Discussion Paper: Short presentation
- ✓ Group dynamic | Klaxoon platform: What are the needs of the area covered by the MAP in relation to Social Dimension?

- *2nd Meeting | online*

The agenda of this 1st meeting was:

- ✓ Main results of the 1st MAP meeting - Identification of needs
- ✓ 1st exercise to answer the following questions - "Examples of policy interventions already in place, at the level of "Improving the well-being of the rural population" and "Promoting social inclusion (migrants)", in the region of MAP SW? "; "Examples of actions undertaken by local actors addressing these needs implemented in the region of MAP SW? "

- ✓ 2nd exercise "What policy interventions are recommended by MAP members to be implemented at local, regional and/or national level, and how can the EU support these interventions, at a Local, Regional and National level"
- ✓ 3rd exercise "What are the knowledge gaps, and what are the research priorities for this region, at Social Dimension?"

EXERCÍCIO 1

Exemplos de intervenções políticas já em curso, ao nível de digitalização, no regime do Fundo?

post-it

Exemplos de ações empreendidas pelos atores locais que abordem estas necessidades implementadas no Fundo?

post-it

EXERCÍCIO 2

Que intervenções políticas são recomendadas pelos membros de TIGOP para serem implementadas a nível local, regional e/ou nacional, e como pode a UE apoiar estas intervenções?

LOCAL

REGIONAL

NACIONAL

INSTRUMENTOS DE MEDIDA

post-it

post-it

post-it

EXERCÍCIO 3

Quais são as lacunas de conhecimento, e que nova investigação é necessária?

LACUNAS DE CONHECIMENTO

post-it

PRORIDADES DE INVESTIGAÇÃO

post-it

Figure 7 -Exercises developed by the MAP Members in individual reflection

- *Validation of the MAP Position Paper*

After the meetings, all collected inputs was worked on and analysed, resulting in a MAP SW Position Paper. This document, written in English, was translated into Portuguese, and sent by email to MAP Members for final validation. Afterwards it has been sent to the SHERPA project.

- *Sharing the SHERPA Position Paper*

Once the SHERPA Position Paper is finalised, it is shared by email with all MAP members.

EXERCÍCIO 1

Exemplos de intervenções políticas já em curso, no nível do Município de bom-custo da população rural e de Promoção da inclusão social no Substrato Alentejano?

Exemplos de ações empreendidas pelas atores locais que abordam estas necessidades implementadas no Substrato Alentejano?

EXERCÍCIO 2

Que intervenções políticas são recomendadas pelos membros de MUP para serem implementadas a nível local, regional e/ou nacional, e como pode a UE apoiar estas intervenções?

EXERCÍCIO 3

Qual o impacto que a UE tem na agricultura? Qual o impacto que a UE tem na agricultura? Qual o impacto que a UE tem na agricultura?

Figure 8 – Results of discussion at the MAP in the klaxon board

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